

**EXISTING PROBLEMS IN THE CONDUCT OF WORK ON
ADMINISTRATIVE OFFENSES AND THEIR SOLUTION****Baxodirov Shodiyor Elyor o'g'li**

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The reforms carried out during the years of independence laid the foundation for the democratization and liberalization of the judicial sphere, increasing its role and importance in protecting the rights and legitimate interests of citizens. The role and significance of crime prevention in the policy of combating crime in our republic have significantly increased. In this regard, during 2023, effective measures were implemented in the activities of internal affairs bodies in conducting cases of administrative offenses in our country. As a result, due to the effective conduct of administrative activities by internal affairs bodies, the number of identified administrative violations in crime prevention for the first 9 months of 2023 amounted to 511,599 cases. Of these, 419,108 were committed by men, 92,491 by women, and 168,612 by young people (aged 18-30). Administrative offenses identified by internal affairs bodies included 42,984 cases of insult (Article 41 of the Code of Administrative Offenses), 23,597 cases of causing minor bodily harm (Article 52 of the Code of Administrative Offenses), 63,258 cases of petty hooliganism (Article 183 of the Code of Administrative Offenses), 16,875 cases of driving a vehicle while intoxicated (Article 131 of the Code of Administrative Offenses), 5,336 cases of drivers and other road users evading examination for intoxication (Article 136 of the Code of Administrative Offenses), and 69,658 cases of engaging in passenger transportation activities without a license (Article 176-3 of the Code of Administrative Offenses). The cases of individuals who committed these offenses were processed by internal affairs bodies based on the rules established in the Code of Administrative Offenses and forwarded to the courts.

In addition, to effectively organize the activities of internal affairs bodies in handling administrative offense cases, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan issued a decision on July 8, 2021, "On additional measures to introduce an electronic system for handling administrative offense cases," which implemented the "E-ma'muriy ish" information system. To further enhance the scope of work in this area, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ZRU-854 dated July 11, 2023, "On Amendments and Additions to Certain Legislative Acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan in Connection with the Improvement of Legislation in the Fields of Ecology and Public Order Protection" was adopted. This law

further improved the procedures for internal affairs bodies to process and review administrative offense cases.

Including:

firstly, by this Law, officials and officials of the oil and gas inspection service of internal affairs bodies are authorized to carry out inspections in accordance with Articles 90, 56, 1 of the Code of Administrative Offenses of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in accordance with Articles 91, 1st, 2nd and 3rd of the Code of Administrative Offenses of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in accordance with Articles 91, 2nd, 1st of the Code of Administrative Offenses of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in accordance with Articles 91, 1st, 1st of the Code of Administrative Offenses of the In addition, in 2020, in Samarkand, 4823 administrative violations were identified by internal affairs bodies, which are significant in preventing violations and crimes, and the state of each case was timely, comprehensively, and objectively determined, and sent to the courts in accordance with Article 282 of the Code of Administrative Offenses.

Among these, 120 cases involved parents failing to fulfill their obligations, 164 cases of inflicting minor bodily harm, 265 cases of minor hooliganism, 545 cases of consuming alcoholic beverages in public places, 15 cases of engaging in prostitution, 114 cases of failing to comply with the lawful demands of internal affairs officers, 15 cases of violating administrative control rules, and 3,585 cases of violating traffic safety rules. As a result, 607 citizens had their vehicles placed in impound lots. Administrative detention was imposed on 149 individuals who committed administrative offenses. During personal searches conducted under Article 290 of the Code of Administrative Offenses, internal affairs bodies confiscated 81 illegal items from citizens (78 knives, 2 brass knuckles, 1 bat). From the above statistics, it can be seen that today, when handling cases of administrative offenses, the internal affairs bodies are proceeding in accordance with Article 272 of the Code of Administrative Offenses, based on the equality of citizens before the law and the body (official) reviewing the case, regardless of gender, social origin, personal and social status, race, nationality, language, religion, or beliefs.

In practice, there are problems hindering the effective handling of administrative offense cases by internal affairs bodies. One such issue is Article 281, which was added to the Code of Administrative Offenses by the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. URQ-829 dated April 11, 2023, "On introducing amendments and additions to certain legislative acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan in connection with further improvement of the system of reliable

protection of rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of women and children." According to Article 281, the supervision of the execution of the punishment of compulsory involvement in paid public works is assigned to the probation units of internal affairs bodies. However, the enforcement mechanism that exists for other types of punishments has not been established for this penalty. Therefore, to address these issues, it is necessary to create an enforcement mechanism for the punishment of compulsory involvement in paid public works as stipulated in Article 281 of the Code of Administrative Offenses.

References:

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